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Review Article

Determination Of Selective COX-2 Inhibitors By Analytical And Bioanalytical Methods : A Review

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ABSTRACT

NSAIDs, or non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medicines, suppress the inflammatory mediator enzyme cyclooxygenase (COX) in order to reduce inflammation. The development of newer NSAIDs, such as celecoxib, rofecoxib, etoricoxib, lumoxicob, and valdecoxib, is responsible for the discovery of COX-2-specific inhibitors, or coxibs. Their usage is limited to the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis, an inflammatory illness characterized by inflammation of the joint lining, which leads to pain, edema, stiffness, joint degeneration, and loss of joint function. The deterioration of the cartilage that surrounds joints, particularly weight-bearing joints, is known as osteoarthritis and is treated with selective COX-2 inhibitors. This analysis's primary goal is to provide both qualitative and quantitative information about selective COX-2 inhibitors in pharmaceutical and biological formulations. In this review article, we have summarized UV/Vis spectroscopy, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), High-performance thin-layer chromatography (HPTLC), Liquid chromatography-mass spectroscopy-mass spectroscopy (LC-MS/MS), and ultra performance liquid chromatography (UPLC) etc. Based methods for estimation of Selective COX-2 inhibitors. In addition to that, we have discussed the bioanalytical methods for Selective COX-2 inhibitors analysis. In conclusion, this review article will help to research scholars for further method development for drug estimation in pharmaceutical dosage

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forms and biological fluids.

INTRODUCTION

In clinical practice, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs) are frequently used to treat pain, inflammation, and fever. Because NSAIDs inhibit the cyclooxygenase (COX) enzyme, they impede prostaglandin synthesis, which accounts for their pharmacological actions. In humans, the enzyme cyclooxygenase (COX) comes in two forms: COX-1 and COX-2. COX-1 is necessary for numerous physiological housekeeping processes, including platelet aggregation, renal homeostasis maintenance, and gastric mucosa protection. Prostaglandins, which mediate reactions to pathologic processes like pain, fever, and inflammation, are synthesized by COX-2.(53) COX is inhibited by NSAIDs. Nevertheless, despite their advantageous benefits, they often conflict with the body's defenses against stomach lining deterioration and platelet dysfunction. As a result, many patients may find that their toxicity-related symptoms are unacceptable. The invention of more recent medications known as COX-2-specific inhibitors (coxibs), such as celecoxib, rofecoxib, etoricoxib, lumoxicob, and valdecoxib, was made possible by this. They maintain the integrity of the stomach lining or platelet control while inhibiting inflammatory disorders. Selective COX-2 inhibitors are as effective as nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), but they have a far better safety record, making it acceptable to use them to treat both acute and chronic pain, with or without inflammatory disorders. It is used to treat the signs and symptoms of osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis. An autoimmune condition called rheumatoid arthritis damages and destroys joints by inflaming the lining of the joints, causing pain, stiffness, swelling, and loss of joint function. The substance that cushions joints wears down over

time, usually in weight-bearing joints, and this leads to osteoarthritis.(22)

CELECOXIB:

A specific inhibitor of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) is celecoxib. This medication is licensed to treat the inflammation-related signs and symptoms of osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis. Celecoxib predominantly inhibits COX-2 but not COX-1 in humans at therapeutic levels. Celecoxib has a better safety profile as compared to traditional non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medicines (NSAIDs), which block both cyclooxygenases. First of all Clinical research has shown that celecoxib effectively reduces edema, discomfort, and sensitivity in the joints while also lowering the risk of stomach ulcers. Furthermore, new research has shown that COX-2 inhibitors reduce the growth of colon polyps.(2) The chemical name of celecoxib is (4-[5-(4-methylphenyl)-3-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-pyrazol-1yl] benzenesulfonamide).(1)

**Figure 1: Chemical Structure of Celecoxib
ETORICOXIB:**

In the group of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) the newest addition of etoricoxib takes place known as selective cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitors. The chemical name of etoricoxib is {5-chloro-3-(4-methanesulfonylphenyl)-6-methyl-[2,3]-bipyridinyl}. In 38 countries worldwide in Europe, Latin America and the Asia Pacific region ETX has been launched. The new drug application (NDA) has submitted a for ARCOXIA (etoricoxib) to the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (USFDA) by Merck & Co. Inc., for the treatment of osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, chronic low back pain, acute pain, dysmenorrheal, acute gouty arthritis and ankylosing spondylitis.(54)

**Figure 2: Chemical Structure of Etoricoxib
VALDECOXIB:**

Valdecoxib is a diaryl substituted isoxazole with the trade name Vx2 (Novartis). The molecular weight of valdecoxib is 314.36. The chemical name of VDX is 4-(5-methyl-3-phenyl-4-isoxazolyl)benzene sulphonamide. It is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) that exhibits anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antipyretic properties which is use for the treatment of osteoarthritis and Rheumatoid arthritis. Even chronic administration of valdecoxib would not increase the risk of cardiac arrhythmia associated with QT prolongation to patients for the treatment of osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis like disease. Valdecoxib is official only in the martindale extra pharmacopoeia.(103) Valdecoxib was immediately banned by Government decision (GSR NO- 510E) from 28-07-2005 after evidence showed its prolonged used leads to increased risk of heart attacks and stroke.(162)

Figure 3: Chemical Structure of Valdecoxib

PARECOXIB:

Parecoxib is a prodrug of valdecoxib. It is a selective cyclooxygenase 2 (COX 2) inhibitor. Parecoxib administered intramuscularly or intravenously in the body.(131) Parecoxib has little or no effect on platelet function. PRX have longer duration of action and it reduced gastrointestinal risk which is considered advantageous in the postoperative repair. Parecoxib can be rapidly hydrolysed into its valdecoxib which is a active metabolite of PRX, and valdecoxib further metabolized by cytochrome P450 enzymes (CYP) into hydroxylated valdecoxib (OH-VX) as the major metabolite. However, the overdosing valdecoxib have been reported for renal safety and high risk of

cardiovascular events of concerns. Therefore, it is necessary to monitor the parecoxib and its metabolites concentration in blood in order to control the concentration of valdecoxib in a reasonable range.(132)

Figure 4: Chemical Structure of Parecoxib

ROFECOXIB:

Rofecoxib belongs to the class of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) called as selective cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitor (COX-2), which gives anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antipyretic effects. RFX is used for osteoarthritis symptoms, dysmenorrhea, and acute pain.(136) Rofecoxib is chemically known as 4-[4-(methylsulfonyl)phenyl]-3-phenyl-2(5H)-furanone.(138) The rofecoxib was voluntarily withdrawn from the global markets because it increased risk of coronary thrombosis and cerebrovascular risk after its chronic use (about 18 months). However, for research purposes comprising characterization

studies, preparation of new formulations, and also in clinical studies rofecoxib is currently used. According to Biopharmaceutics Classification System (low solubility and high permeability) RFX is a Class II compound and it has a long half-life ($t_{1/2} = 17$ h). Therefore, In the formulation studies of controlled release dosage forms, and also in new drug delivery systems it is used as a model drug.(136) Rofecoxib was immediately banned by Government decision (GSR NO-810E) from 13-12-2004 after evidence showed its prolonged used leads to increased risk of heart attacks.(162)

Figure 5: Chemical Structure of Rofecoxib
LUMIRACOXIB:

Lumiracoxib is a selective cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitor developed for the symptomatic treatment of osteoarthritis and acute pain. Lumiracoxib chemically known as 2-[(2-fluoro-6-

chlorophenyl)amino]-5-methyl benzeneacetic acid.(157) The molecular weight of LMX is 294 Da. Lumiracoxib is chemically differ from the other COX-2 inhibitors that it lacks a sulfur-containing moiety and possesses a carboxylic group that confers weakly acidic properties (pK_a 4.7). It was recently withdrawn from the market in some countries, however it could be available in others.(161)

Figure 6: Chemical Structure of Lumiracoxib
Analytical techniques used for determination of Selective COX-2 inhibitors:

For the determination of Selective COX-2 inhibitors in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations, an exhaustive literature search found numerous analytical techniques such as UV/Visible Spectrophotometry, HPLC, HPTLC, UPLC, LC-MS/MS, and bioanalytical approaches. Figure 7 shows different analytical methods

implemented for the estimation of Selective COX-2 inhibitors

Figure 7: Analytical methods of Selective COX-2 Inhibitors

CELECOXIB:

Bio-analytical method for CXB

Bio-analysis is a sub-discipline of analytical chemistry covering the quantitative measurement of xenobiotics (drugs and their metabolites, and biological molecules in unnatural locations or concentrations) and biotics (macromolecules, proteins, DNA, large molecule drugs, metabolites) in biological systems. The summary of the reported bioanalytical methods is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Bioanalytical determination of CXB

Sr. No.	Drug	Sample Matrix	Method	Column	Detection	Internal Standard	Ref
1	CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Nova Pak C8 column	215 nm	SC-236	1
2	CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Zorbax Eclipse Extend C18 column	***	Dimethyl - Celecoxib	2
3	CXB	Human plasma and breast milk	HPLC	C18 column	254 nm	***	3
4	CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Monolithic silica column	254 nm	Mefenamic acid	4
5	CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Nucleosil CN column	260 nm	Flutamide	5
6	CXB	Rat plasma	HPLC	C18 analytical column	254 nm	Ibuprofen	6
7	CXB	Rat plasma	HPLC	C18 reverse phase column	254 nm	Ketoprofen	7
8	CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	C18 μ -Bondapak HPLC column	260 nm	Flutamide	8
9	CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Nucleosil-NO column	260 nm	***	9
10	CXB	Human serum	HPLC	Prontosil C AQ column	240 nm	Demethylated analogue	10
11	CXB	Human serum	HPLC	C18 Wakosil column	250 nm	Tolbutamide	11

12	CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Knauer C18 column	250 nm	***	12
13	CXB	Skin samples	HPLC	C18 column	251 nm	Caffeine	13
14	CBX	Human urine	HPLC	Spherigel C18 column	255 nm	***	14
15	CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Nucleosil C8 guard column	260 nm	Rofecoxib	15
16	REP, CXB	Male Sprague-Dawley rats	HPLC	Reversed C18 column	240 nm	Ketoconazole	16
17	RFX, CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Zorbax SB-CN analytical column	254 nm	4- <i>n</i> -pentyl-phenyl-acetic acid	17
18	DTX, CXB	Rat plasma	HPLC	Reversed-phase C18 μ -Bondapack column	230 nm	Paclitaxel	18
19	IBU, DIC, CXB	Human urine	HPLC	MZ ODS-C18 column	330 nm	***	19
20	DIC, RFX, NIF, CXB	Human serum	HPLC	C18 bonded silica column	261 nm, 288 nm, 282 nm, 254 nm	***	20
21	CXB, OH-CXB, COOH-CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	C18 reverse phase column	254 nm	Phenacetin	21
22	ETX, SCA, VDX, KPF, NMS, CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Kromasil KR 100-5C18 column	235 nm	DRF-4367	22
23	CXB	Human plasma	LC-MS	Shim Pack GLC-CN, C column	***	Sulindac	23
24	CXB	Rat blood	UPLC-MS/MS	Phenomenex Aqua C18	254nm	1-(4-sulfamoylphenyl)-5-(<i>p</i> -tolyl)-1 <i>H</i> -pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid	24
25	CXB	Rat and human liver microsomes	UPLC-MS/MS	UPLC BEH C18 column	***	Carbamazepine	25

26	ETX, CXB	Serum and synovial fluid of inflammatory arthritis patients	UPLC/ICPMS	Acquity C18 BEH	***	***	26
27	CBX, DEZ, DEX	Beagle plasma	UPLC-MS/MS	UPLC BEH C18 column	***	Midazolam	27

*** Not Provided

UV-Visible spectroscopy method for CXB

The spectrophotometric methods have been accounted for the determination of CXB. The details of Spectrophotometry determination of

basic principle, sample matrix, lambda max, solvent linearity range and the correlation coefficient are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Spectrophotometric methods used for determination of CXB

Sr. No.	Drug	Matrix	Solvent	Lambda Max (nm)	Linearity (µg/mL)	Correlation coefficient (R2)	Ref.
1	CXB	Capsule	Either ethanol or acetonitrile	272 nm	0–3 mg/L	Ethanol = 0.995 Acetonitrile = 0.999	28
2	CXB	Capsule	Methanol	270 nm	10 to 50 µg/ml	0.9965	29
3	CXB	In pure form and In solid dosage form	High pure water, methanol, acetonitrile	251 nm	1–20 µg/ml	0.9999	30
4	AMD and CXB	In Pharmaceutical Formulation	Ethanol	364.3nm and 286.7nm	0.5 to 10 µg/ml and 5 to 40 µg/ml	0.9992 and 0.9990	31
5	CXB and AMD	Tablets	Methanol	250 nm And 290 nm	15–40 µg/ml and 3–8 µg/ml	0.9992 and 0.9991	32
6	AMD, CXB and RMP	Pharmaceutical combined dosage forms	Methanol	361 nm, 253nm and 222 nm	5–60 µg/ml, 5–30 µg/ml, and 5–110 µg/ml	0.9998, 0.9998 and 1	33
7	AMD and CXB	Pure and pharmaceutical Formulation	Ethanol	334.2 nm and 254.2 nm	1–6 µg/ml and 5–40 µg/ml	0.9994 and 0.9999	34

*** Not Provided

Liquid-Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy methods (LC-MS) for CXB:

In recent years, the combination of LC/MS has gained a lot of attention for the analysis of interest analytes in complex samples with improved performance. In brief, after a thorough examination, LC/MS interfaces are divided into two categories namely interfaces for indirect and direct input of column effluent. A mechanical mechanism is employed to transmit the column effluent to the MS vacuum at an indirect

introduction interface. A classic example of an indirect introduction type of interface is the transportation system. In the case of the direct introduction system, the column effluent flows directly into the mass spectrometric vacuum system via a tube. Mainly, the most straightforward method of linking LC and MS appears to be the direct introduction.³³ In this section, we have discussed the LC-MS methods for the determination of CXB in a dosage form Table 3.

Table 3. Summary of LC-MS methods for the determination of CXB in a dosage form

Sr. No	Drug	Matrix	Stationary Phase	Mobile Phase	Internal Standard	Linearity (ng/mL)	Ref.
1	CXB	***	Symmetry C18 analytical column	5.0 mm ammonium acetate-acetonitrile in the ratio of 30:70 (v/v)	***	0.06 to 3.0 ppm	36
2	CXB	Bulk and formulations using a chiral column	Chiralcel OD column	Hexane: Ethanol (94:06 v:v)	***	0.25–0.75 mg:ml	37

*** Not Provided

HPLC method for CXB

The specificity of the HPLC method is excellent and simultaneously sufficient precision is also attainable. However, it has to be stated that the astonishing specificity, precision, and accuracy are attainable only if wide-ranging system suitability

tests are carried before the HPLC analysis. For this reason, the expense to be paid for the high specificity, precision, and accuracy is also high. The summary of the reported HPLC methods is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of HPLC methods for the determination of CXB in a single and combined dosage form

Sr. No.	Drug name	Column	Mobile phase	Lambda max (nm)	Linearity (µg/mL)	Retention time (min)	Flow rate (mL/min)	Detector	Ref.
1	CXB	Inertsil ODS-3 column	Acetonitrile : water (55:45 v/v)	242 nm	0.25 to 1.0 µg/ml	16.55 min	1.0 ml/min	SPD-M10AVP photodiode array detector	38
2	CXB	Column L11	Buffer, Methanol and Acetonitrile	215nm	25-120 µg/ml	23.501 min	1.3 ml/min	VWD detector	39

			(60: 30: 10v/v/v)						
3	CXB	Reversed-phase C-18 column	Buffer and acetonitrile (40:60)	254 nm	1 to 150 mg/ml	10.9 min	1 ml/min	Photo-diode array detector	40
4	CXB	Reversed-phase C-18 column	Methanol and water (85:15)	251 nm	2 to 50 mg/ml	4.965 min	0.8 ml/min	Ultraviolet (UV)-visible detector	41
5	CXB	Reversed-phase C-18 column	Methanol and water (75:25 % v/v)	250 nm	0.27–80 µg/ml	4.8 ± 0.01 min	1.25 ml/min	UV–visible detector	42
6	AMD and CXB	Zorbax C18	Sodium phosphate buffer (ph. 5.6) : acetonitrile : methanol in a ratio 30:55:15 (v/v)	239 nm	5–30 µg/ml and 50–500 µg/ml	1.72±0.02 min 3.38±0.023 min	1.2 ml/min	UV detector	43
7	CUR and CXB	RP C18 XDB column	Water (1% acetic acid)-Acetonitrile	254 nm	1- 20 µg/ml and 0.1-2 µg/ml	***	1.50 ml/min	UV/Vis detector	44
8	AMD and CXB	C18 reversed phase column (Thermos ODS Hypersil)	Acetonitrile: potassium phosphate Buffer 60:40 (v/v)	360 nm and 265 nm	0.017 and 0.0167 µg/ml	4.41min and 7.30 min	1 ml/min	UV detector	45
9	AMD and CXB	Reversed-phase C-18 column	MEOH + Water (70 : 30 v/v)	235 nm	1-5 µg/ml and 20-100 µg/ml	3.953 min and 6.587 min.	1 ml/min	UV Detector	46
10	ATV-Ca and CXB	Cosmosil-C18 column	Acetonitrile: ammonium acetate buffer: methanol (50 : 25 : 25 v/v/v)	277nm	100-500µg/ml	6.195 min and 3.989min	1.0ml/min	UV/Vis detector	47
11	CXB and AMD	Kromasil C18 column	Methanol and potassium dihydrogen phosphate	253 nm	10-60 µg/ml and 1-6 µg/ml	2.89 min and 5.89 min	1.2 ml/min	UV Detector	48

			70 : 30% v/v						
12	CXB and DIN	Inertsil ODS 3V L1 column	Methanol and acetonitrile; 50 : 50, v/v	255 nm	10-40 µg/ml and 5-20 µg/ml	7.42 min and 13.96 min	1.0ml/min	Photodiode array detector	49
13	AMD and CXB	Florosil C18 analytical column	Acetonitrile- Water (80:20 v/v)	250 nm	2-12 µg/ml and 50-300 µg/ml	1.98 min and 3.18 min	1.0ml/min	UV/Vis detector	50

HPTLC method for CXB

Thin-layer chromatography is a popular technique for the analysis of a wide variety of organic and inorganic materials, because of its distinctive advantages such as minimal sample clean-up, a

wide choice of mobile phases, flexibility in sample distinction, high sample loading capacity and low cost. The summary of the reported HPTLC methods is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Summary of HPTLC methods for the determination of CXB in a single and combined dosage form

Sr. No.	Drug	Stationary Phase	Mobile Phase	Detection	Linearity	Ref.
1	CXB	Silica gel 60F254	N-hexane-ethyl acetate, 60 + 40 (v/v)	262 nm	200 and 2000 ng/spot	51
2	AMD and CXB	Pre-coated silica gel aluminum Plate 60 F254	Toluene : ammonia : methanol : acetonitrile (6.6:0.12:1.5:2 v/v/v/v)	240 nm	0.3-2 µg/spot 0.3-3.4 µg/spot	52

ETORICOXIB:

Bio-analytical method for ETX

Bio-analysis is a sub-discipline of analytical chemistry covering the quantitative measurement of xenobiotics (drugs and their metabolites, and biological molecules in unnatural locations or

concentrations) and biotics (macromolecules, proteins, DNA, large molecule drugs, metabolites) in biological systems. The summary of the reported bioanalytical methods is shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Bioanalytical determination of ETX

Sr. No.	Drug	Sample Matrix	Method	Column	Detection	Internal Standard	Ref
1	ETX	Human plasma	HPLC	Hypersil BDS, C18 column	235 nm	Valdecoxib in acetonitrile	53
2	ETX	Human plasma	HPLC	Waters symmetry® C18 column	284 nm	Zaleplon	54

3	ETX	Human plasma	HPLC	Waters symmetry® C18 column	284 nm	Rofecoxib	55
4	ETX	Rat Plasma	HPLC	Novapak-C8 column	245 nm	Flurbiprofen	56
5	ETX	Human plasma	LC-APCI/MS/MS	Luna C18 column	***	Antipyrin	57
6	ETX	Human plasma	LC-MS-MS	Narrow bore RP C column	***	Phenazone	58
7	ETX	Human plasma	LC-MS/MS	Thermo Hypurity, C18 column	***	Etoricoxib D3	59
8	ETX	Spiked Human plasma	LC-MS/MS	C18 analytical column	234 nm	Piroxicam	60
9	ETX and VDX	Human plasma	RP-HPLC	Nucleosil C8 guard column	***	TO FIND IT	61
10	ETX, SCA, VDX, KPF, NMS, CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Kromasil KR 100-5C18 column	235 nm	DRF-4367	62
11	ETX	Human plasma	UPLC-MS/MS	ACQUITY UPLC HSS T3 column	***	Etoricoxib-d3	63
12	RLZ and ETX	Rat plasma and brain tissue	LC-MS/MS	ACQUITY UPLC BEH C18 column	***	Etoricoxib D4	64

*** Not Provided

UV-Visible spectroscopy method for ETX

The spectrophotometric methods have been accounted for the determination of ETX. The details of Spectrophotometry determination of

basic principle, sample matrix, lambda max, solvent linearity range and the correlation coefficient are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7: Spectrophotometric methods used for determination of ETX

Sr. No.	Drug	Matrix	Solvent	Lambda Max (nm)	Linearity (µg/mL)	Correlation coefficient (R2)	Ref.
1	ETX	Bulk and tablet Formulation	0.1N HCl	233 nm	2-24 µg/ml	0.9996	65
2	ETX	Tablet dosage form	0.1 N HCl	271.6 nm	1-25µg/ml	0.9981	66

3	ETX	Bulk and Tablet Formulation	Methanol	234nm	1 to 11 µg/ml	0.9986	67
4	ETX	Pharmaceutical formulations	0.1 M HCl	233 nm	0.1–0.5 µg/ml	0.997	68
5	ETX and DRT	Combined tablet dosage form	Methanol	274nm and 351 nm	4.5-22.5 µg/ml and 4-20 µg/ml	***	69
6	ETX and THC	Bulk and combined tablet dosage form	0.1N HCl	240 nm and 260 nm	2.5–30 µg/ml	0.9999	70

*** Not Provided

Liquid-Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy methods (LC-MS) for ETX:

In recent years, the combination of LC/MS has gained a lot of attention for the analysis of interest analytes in complex samples with improved performance. In brief, after a thorough examination, LC/MS interfaces are divided into two categories namely interfaces for indirect and direct input of column effluent. A mechanical mechanism is employed to transmit the column effluent to the MS vacuum at an indirect

introduction interface. A classic example of an indirect introduction type of interface is the transportation system. In the case of the direct introduction system, the column effluent flows directly into the mass spectrometric vacuum system via a tube. Mainly, the most straightforward method of linking LC and MS appears to be the direct introduction. In this section, we have discussed the LC-MS methods for the determination of ETX in a dosage form Table 8.

Table 8. Summary of LC-MS methods for the determination of ETX in a dosage form

Sr. No	Drug	Matrix	Stationary Phase	Mobile Phase	Internal Standard	Linearity (µg/mL)	Ref.
1	ETX	Pharmaceutical dosage forms	Synergi fusion C18 column	0.01M phosphoric acid – acetonitrile (62 + 38, v/v)	Piroxicam	0.02–150 µg/ml	71

HPLC method for ETX

The specificity of the HPLC method is excellent and simultaneously sufficient precision is also attainable. However, it has to be stated that the astonishing specificity, precision, and accuracy are attainable only if wide-ranging system suitability

tests are carried before the HPLC analysis. For this reason, the expense to be paid for the high specificity, precision, and accuracy is also high. The summary of the reported HPLC methods is shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Summary of HPLC methods for the determination of ETX in a single and combined dosage form

Sr. No	Drug name	Column	Mobile phase	Lambda max (nm)	Linearity (µg/mL)	Retention time (min)	Flow rate (mL/min)	Detector	Ref.
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1	ETX	Hyper ODS 2 C18 column	Methanol	233 nm	20-55 µg/ml	3.28 min	1 ml/min	UV-Visible	72
2	ETX	Reverse phase C18 column	Acetonitrile : Ammonium Acetate buffer (50:50)	235 nm	20-75 µg/ml	5.337 min	1 ml/min	UV-Visible	73
3	ETX	Inertsil ODS-4 column	0.01M sodium perchlorate monohydrate and acetonitrile (48:52 v/v)	235 nm	34.44-63.96 µg/ml	4.299 min	1.5 ml/min	UV detector	74
4	ETX	Reverse phase C18 column	Methanol: phosphate buffer (90:10 v/v)	235 nm	10-200 µg/ml	3.428 min	1ml/min	UV detector	75
5	ETX	Kromasil 100, RP-C18 Column	Acetonitrile : methanol : 10mm potassium dihydrogen phosphate (35:35:30 v/v)	234 nm	25 to 400 ng/injection	***	1 ml/min	UV/VIS detector	76
6	ETX	Phenomenex ODS 2 C18 column	Methanol : 10mM Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate (75:25 % v/v)	287 nm	4.99–99.70 µg/ml	3.2 min	0.8 ml/min	UV detector	77
7	ETX	BDS-Hypersil C-8 column	Water : acetonitrile : methanol (50 : 25 :25 v/v/v)	284 nm	5 -50 µg/ml	4.8 min	1.25 ml/min	UV detector	78
8	ETX	ODS Hypersil C18 column	Acetonitrile: water (55:45 v/v)	269 nm	10 to 60 µg/ml	5.03 min	0.9ml/min	UV/VIS detector	79

9	ETX	Hypersil ODS C-18 column	Acetonitrile and potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (46:54 % v/v)	280 nm	0.5-85.0 µg/ml	3.083 min	1.2 ml/min	UV detector	80
10	ETX	Zorbax SB CN column	Disodium hydrogen orthophosphate (0.02 M) : acetonitrile (60:40)	235 nm	***	11.510 min	0.8 ml / min	***	81
11	THC and ETX	BDS Hypersil C18 column	Acetonitrile : Buffer (75 :25)	220nm	***	3.97 min and 7.46 min	1.5 ml/min	***	82
12	THC and ETX	Zorbax C-18 analytical column	Methanol and water (60:40)	283 nm	2 to 20 µg/ml and 10 to 200 µg/ml	3.523 min and 9.627 min	0.7 ml/min	UV detector	83
13	PCT and ETX	Kromasil C18 column	Buffer : Acetonitrile	220 nm	48 to 146 µg/ml and 6 to 19 µg/ml	8.34 min and 18.45 min	1.0 ml/min	UV-VIS detector	84
14	THC and ETX	BDS Hypersil C-18 column	Trifluoroacetic acid buffer and acetonitrile (75:25, v/v)	220 nm	2 to 16 ppm and 20 to 160 ppm	3.1 min and 6.6 min	1.5 ml/min	UV detector	85
15	PCT and ETX	Phenomenex Luna C18 column	Methanol : water (70:30 v/v)	235 nm	5-30 µg/ml	3.07 min and 5.72 min	1.0 ml/min	UV detector	86
16	PGBN and ETX	Thermo C18 column	Orthophosphoric acid (0.1%) : methanol (60:40 v/v)	236 nm	37.5 to 112.5 µg/ml and 30 to 90 µg/ml	2.636 min and 5.607 min	1.0 ml/min	Waters photodiode detector	87
17	THC and ETX	Hypersil BDS C18 column	Phosphate buffer(ph-3.4) and acetonitrile (35:65 v/v)	260nm	2.5-15 µg/ml and 5.0-30 µg/ml	2.83 min And 6.92min	1.0 ml/min	UV detector	88

18	PGBN and ETX	Hypersil ODS, C18 column	Methanol: acetonitrile: phosphate buffer (pH 5) (40:20:20)	215 nm	12.5–37.5 µg/ml and 150–450 µg/ml	3.523 min and 4.702 min	1.0 ml/min	UV-VIS detector	89
19	ETX and PCT	Hypersil ODS, C18 column	0.05 M sodium dihydrogen phosphate buffer : acetonitrile (35:65 v/v)	235nm	50-150% of the working standard solution concentration	1.889 min and 2.460 min	1.0 ml/min	UV-VIS detector	90
20	KPF, ETX and DIC	C18 column	50% Cetrimide and 50% acetonitrile for KPF and ETX 30% Cetrimide and 70% acetonitrile for DIC	254 nm, 234 nm, and 254 nm	0.03- 0.50 mg/ml , 0.007- 0.11 mg/ml and 0.016 - 0.250 mg/ml	9.41 min, 7.34 min, and 6.66 min	1.0 ml/min	UV detector	91
21	PCT and ETX	Inertsil ODS, C8-3 column	Methanol: acetonitrile: phosphate buffer (40:20:40 v/v)	242 nm	50 to 150 µg/ml and 6-18µg/ml	3.27min, 6.12 min	1.0 ml/min	***	92
22	THC and ETX	Inertsil C18 column	Acetonitrile: pH 3 phosphate buffer (70:30% v/v)	254nm	25-125 µg/ml and 15-75 µg/ml	2.325 min and 4.296 min	1.0 ml/min	UV detector	93
23	ETX and PCT	PURITAS TM EXIMIUS C18 analytical column	Acetonitrile and 0.1 percent acetic acid in water (70:30V/V)	235nm	20-120ppm and 20-200ppm	4.2 min and 2.1 min	1.0 ml/min	PDA detector	94
24	ETX and PCT	Phenomenex® C18 column	Acetonitrile, methanol	236 nm	8.3-41.5 µg/ml and 1-5 µg/ml	5.472 min, 7.650 min	1.0 ml/min	UV detector	95

			and water 60:15:25 (v/v/v)						
25	TOP and ETX	Eclips plus C18 column	0.035M triethylam ine and acetonitril e (70:30 v/v)	290nm	5-15 µg/ml	2.826 min and 7.566 min	1.0 ml/min	PDA detector	96
26	PGBN and ETX	Ascentis C18 column	Acetonitri le and 0.01N potassium dihydroge n phosphate (50: 50)	228nm	***	2.313 min and 2.840 min	0.8 ml/min	PDA detector	97

*** Not Provided

HPTLC method for ETX

Thin-layer chromatography is a popular technique for the analysis of a wide variety of organic and inorganic materials, because of its distinctive advantages such as minimal sample clean-up, a

wide choice of mobile phases, flexibility in sample distinction, high sample loading capacity and low cost. The summary of the reported HPTLC methods is shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Summary of HPTLC methods for the determination of ETX in a single and combined dosage form

Sr. No.	Drug	Stationary Phase	Mobile Phase	Detection	Linearity	Ref.
1	ETX	Precoated silica gel 60F ₂₅₄	Chloroform: methanol: toluene (4:2:4 v/v)	289 nm	100 to 600 ng/spot	98
2	ETX	Precoated silica gel 60F ₂₅₄	Toluene–1,4-dioxane– methanol 8.5:1.0:0.5 (v/v)	235 nm	100 to 1500 ng/spot	99
3	PCT and ETX	Precoated silica gel 60F ₂₅₄	Toluene: ethylacetate: methanol in the ratio of 6: 4: 1 (v/v/v)	263 nm	60-360 ng/spot 50-300 ng/spot	100
4	ETX and THC	Precoated silica gel 60F ₂₅₄	Ethyl acetate–methanol (8 + 2, v/v)	290 nm	50–250 and 100–500 ng/band	101

UPLC methods for ETX

Ultra-performance liquid chromatography (UPLC) is a new category of separation based on well-established principles of liquid chromatography, which utilizes sub-2-mm

particles for the stationary phase. The developed UPLC method is validated and therefore could be further used for quantitative analysis of Etoricoxib. Sanjay Shesha Shetgar^{1*}, Ramadevi Dharmasoth², Bandlamudi Mallikarjuna Rao³,

Basavaiah Keloth⁴ established UPLC method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of Etoricoxib and Thiocolchicoside in tablets. UPLC was carried out in Hibar, C18 column of dimension 100 × 2.1 mm, 1.8 μm, at 30°C, by using mobile phase 0.1% orthophosphoric acid (pH 2.5) and acetonitrile in a ratio of 90:10 (v/v). The column effluents were monitored at 256 nm using a Acquity Tunable UV detector at a flow rate of 0.3 ml/minute. The linearity of the calibration curve ranged from 1–6 μg/ml of Thiocolchicoside and 15–90 μg/ml of Etoricoxib and the regression coefficient (r²) was

0.999 for both Etoricoxib and Thiocolchicoside drugs.(102)

VALDECOXIB:

Bio-analytical method for VDX

Bio-analysis is a sub-discipline of analytical chemistry covering the quantitative measurement of xenobiotics (drugs and their metabolites, and biological molecules in unnatural locations or concentrations) and biotics (macromolecules, proteins, DNA, large molecule drugs, metabolites) in biological systems. The summary of the reported bioanalytical methods is shown in Table 11.

Table 11: Bioanalytical determination of VDX

Sr. No.	Drug	Sample Matrix	Method	Column	Detection	Internal Standard	Ref
1	VDX	Human plasma	HPLC	ODS C18 column	244 nm	Nimesulide	103
2	VDX	Human plasma	HPLC	ODS-AQ column	210 nm	Rofecoxib	104
3	VDX	Human plasma	HPLC	C18 column	240 nm	Celecoxib	105
4	VDX	Human plasma	HPLC	Cosmosil C18 column	239 nm	Rofecoxib	106
5	PRX and VDX	Canine plasma	HPLC	Luna C18 ODS2 analytical columns	265 nm and 375 nm	Celecoxib, Rofecoxib	B5
6	PRX and VDX	Rat plasma	UPLC-MS/MS	ACQUITY UPLC BEH C18 reversed phase column	***	Celecoxib	107
7	PRX and VDX	Beagles' plasma	UPLC-MS/MS	Acquity UPLC BEH C18 column	***	Celecoxib	108
8	PRX and VDX	Rat plasma	UPLC-MS/MS	Kinetex C18 column	***	Ketoprofen	109
9	PRX and VDX	Beagle plasma	UPLC-MS/MS	Acquity UPLC BEH C18 column	***	Celecoxib	110

10	ETX, SCA, VDX, KPF, NMS, CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Kromasil KR 100-5C18 column	235 nm	DRF-4367	111
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*** Not Provided

UV-Visible spectroscopy method for VDX

The spectrophotometric methods have been accounted for the determination of VDX. The details of Spectrophotometry determination of

basic principle, sample matrix, lambda max, solvent linearity range and the correlation coefficient are summarized in Table 12.

Table 12: Spectrophotometric methods used for determination of VDX

Sr. No.	Drug	Matrix	Solvent	Lambda Max (nm)	Linearity (µg/mL)	Correlation coefficient (R2)	Ref.
1	VDX	Pure form and Tablet	0.1N Sodium Hydroxide	243 nm	3-15 µg/mL	0.9998	112
2	VDX	Pure and pharmaceutical dosage forms	1 M sodium hydroxide	610 nm	5-25 mg/ml	0.9999	113
3	VDX and TNZ	Combined tablet dosage form	Methanol	237 nm and 289.5 nm	5-30 µg/mL And 0.5-3.0 µg/mL	0.9999 and 0.9997	114
4	VDX and TZN	Mixture	Methanol:0.1 mHCl (1:1)	243 nm and 228 nm	5-30 µg/ml and 2-20 µg/ml	***	115
5	VDX and PCT	Combined tablet dosage form	0.1 N NaOH	244 nm and 257 nm	1-6 µg/ml and 5-30 µg/ml	1.0	116

*** Not Provided

Liquid-Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy methods (LC-MS) for VDX:

In recent years, the combination of LC/MS has gained a lot of attention for the analysis of interest analytes in complex samples with improved performance. In brief, after a thorough examination, LC/MS interfaces are divided into two categories namely interfaces for indirect and direct input of column effluent. A mechanical mechanism is employed to transmit the column effluent to the MS vacuum at an indirect introduction interface. A classic example of an indirect introduction type of interface is the transportation system. In the case of the direct

introduction system, the column effluent flows directly into the mass spectrometric vacuum system via a tube. Mainly, the most straightforward method of linking LC and MS appears to be the direct introduction.³³ In this section, we have discussed the LC-MS methods for the determination of VDX in a dosage form Table 13.

Table 13. Summary of LC-MS methods for the determination of VDX in a dosage form

Sr. No	Drug	Matrix	Stationary Phase	Mobile Phase	Internal Standard	Linearity (ng/mL)	Ref.
1	VDX	Bulk drug	Agilent Zorbax SB-CN	0.01M potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate : acetonitrile 80:20 (v/v)	***	25 to 150 µg/ml	117

HPLC method for VDX

The specificity of the HPLC method is excellent and simultaneously sufficient precision is also attainable. However, it has to be stated that the astonishing specificity, precision, and accuracy are attainable only if wide-ranging system suitability

tests are carried before the HPLC analysis. For this reason, the expense to be paid for the high specificity, precision, and accuracy is also high. The summary of the reported HPLC methods is shown in Table 14.

Table 14: Summary of HPLC methods for the determination of VDX in a single and combined dosage form

Sr. No.	Drug name	Column	Mobile phase	Lambda max(nm)	Linearity (µg/mL)	Retention time (min)	Flow rate (mL/min)	Detector
1	VDX	Synergi fusion C18 column	Water : acetonitrile (52:48, v/v)	210 nm	0.05-150 µg/ml	5.51 min	1.0 ml/min	PDA detector
2	PCT and VDX	Luna C-18 column	Methanol: phosphate buffer ph. 3.5 (60:40 v/v)	242 nm	25-150 µg/ml and 1-6 µg/ml	3.01 min and 8.51 min	1.0 ml/min	***
3	TNZ and VDX	Hypersil C-18 column	Ammonium acetate buffer (0.1 M): methanol: acetonitrile 50:30:20 v/v	232 nm	1-100 µg/ml	3.2 min and 4.5 min	1 ml/min	UV detector
4	VDX	Phenomenex Luna C18 column	20mm nah2po4, methanol and Tetrahydrofuran 60:30:10 (v/v)	240 nm	***	19.436 min	1.0 ml/min	UV detector
5	VDX	Xterratm RP18 column	0.01M ammonium acetate in water and Acetonitrile 50 : 50 (v/v)	220 nm	***	6.89 min	1ml/min	UV detector
6	VDX	Phenomenex Luna C18 column	Acetonitrile : 0.5% triethylamine (50:50 v/v)	240 nm	0.1-0.5 µg/ml and 1.0-3.0 µg/ml	8.95 min and 10.34 min	1ml/min	***

7	TNZ and VDX	Hypersil BDS C-18 column	0.3% triethylamine and acetonitrile 70:30 v/v	***	***	3.15 min and 10.92 min	***	***
8	TNZ and VDX	Luna C18 column	Acetonitrile: phosphate buffer pH 3.5 (50:50 v/v)	227 nm	0.4-2.0 µg/ml and 4-20 µg/ml	4.43 min and 16.60 min	0.5 ml/min	***
9	TNZ and VDX	C18 Intersil column	Acetonitrile : 0.02M phosphate buffer (ph 3.5) (60:40 v/v)	240 nm	0-20 µg/ml And 0-100 µg/ml	2.16 min and 4.21 min	1.5 ml/min	***

*** Not Provided

HPTLC method for VDX

Thin-layer chromatography is a popular technique for the analysis of a wide variety of organic and inorganic materials, because of its distinctive advantages such as minimal sample clean-up, a

wide choice of mobile phases, flexibility in sample distinction, high sample loading capacity and low cost. The summary of the reported HPTLC methods is shown in Table 15.

Table 15: Summary of HPTLC methods for the determination of VDX in a single and combined dosage form

Sr. No.	Drug	Stationary Phase	Mobile Phase	Detection	Linearity	Ref.
1	VDX	Precoated silica gel aluminum plates 60 GF ₂₅₄	Toluene : acetone : ammonia (5%) 7:5:1 v/v/v	236 nm	200–1000 ng/µL	127
2	VDX and PCT	Pre coated silica gel 60 GF ₂₅₄ TLC plate	Chloroform: isopropyl alcohol: glacial acetic acid (9.5:1:0.2 v/v/v)	250 nm	0.1 to 0.5 µg/spot 2.5 to 12.5 µg/spot	128

PARECOXIB:

Bio-analytical method for PRX

Bio-analysis is a sub-discipline of analytical chemistry covering the quantitative measurement of xenobiotics (drugs and their metabolites, and biological molecules in unnatural locations or

concentrations) and biotics (macromolecules, proteins, DNA, large molecule drugs, metabolites) in biological systems. The summary of the reported bioanalytical methods is shown in Table 16.

Table 16: Bioanalytical determination of PRX

Sr. No.	Drug	Sample Matrix	Method	Column	Detection	Internal Standard	Ref
1	PRX and VDX	Canine plasma	HPLC	C18 ODS2	265 nm	Celecoxib, Rofecoxib	130

				analytical column			
2	PRX	Human plasma	RP-HPLC	CLC C18 column	200 nm	Ibuprofen	131
3	PRX, VDX and OH-VDX	Mouse plasma	LC-MS/MS	Extend-C18 HPLC column	***	Piperaquine	132
4	PRX and VDX	Beagle Plasma	UPLC-MS/MS	Acquity UPLC BEH C18 column	***	Celecoxib	133
5	PRX and VDX	Rat plasma	UPLC-MS/MS	Kinetex C18 column	***	Ketoprofen	134

*** Not Provided

ROFECOXIB:

Bio-analytical method for RFX

Bio-analysis is a sub-discipline of analytical chemistry covering the quantitative measurement of xenobiotics (drugs and their metabolites, and biological molecules in unnatural locations or

concentrations) and biotics (macromolecules, proteins, DNA, large molecule drugs, metabolites) in biological systems. The summary of the reported bioanalytical methods is shown in Table 17.

Table 17: Bioanalytical determination of RFX

Sr. No.	Drug	Sample Matrix	Method	Column	Detection	Internal Standard	Ref
1	RFX	Human serum	HPLC	Novapak-C18 analytical column	254 nm	Diazepam	135
2	RFX	Bovine serum albumin microsphere	HPLC	C18 column	272 nm	***	136
3	RFX	Rat and Human Plasma	HPLC	C18 analytical column	272 nm	Ketoprofen	137
4	RFX	Bulk Drug, Tablets and Human Plasma	HPLC	Spherisorb ODSI column	244 nm	Etodolac	138
5	RFX	Human Plasma	HPLC	BDS-Hypersil C-18 analytical column	250 nm	Not mention name only structure is given	139
6	RFX and CXB	Human plasma	HPLC	Zorbax SB-CN	254 nm	4- <i>n</i> -pentyl-phenyl-acetic acid	140

				analytical column			
7	DIC, RFX, NIF, CXB	Human serum	HPLC	C18 bonded silica column	261 nm, 288 nm, 282 nm, 254 nm	***	141
8	RFX	Human plasma	HPLC-MS	Nucleosil C-8 guard column	***	Celecoxib	142

*** Not Provided

UV-Visible spectroscopy method for RFX

The spectrophotometric methods have been accounted for the determination of RFX. The details of Spectrophotometry determination of

basic principle, sample matrix, lambda max, solvent linearity range and the correlation coefficient are summarized in Table 18.

Table 18: Spectrophotometric methods used for determination of RFX

Sr. No.	Drug	Matrix	Solvent	Lambda Max (nm)	Linearity (µg/mL)	Correlation coefficient (R2)	Ref.
1	RFX and MSPC	Individual dosage form	Methanol	282 nm and 331 nm	10-50 ng/ml 2-10 ng/ml	0.9990 0.9996	143

Liquid-Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy methods (LC-MS) for RFX:

In recent years, the combination of LC/MS has gained a lot of attention for the analysis of interest analytes in complex samples with improved performance. In brief, after a thorough examination, LC/MS interfaces are divided into two categories namely interfaces for indirect and direct input of column effluent. A mechanical mechanism is employed to transmit the column effluent to the MS vacuum at an indirect

introduction interface. A classic example of an indirect introduction type of interface is the transportation system. In the case of the direct introduction system, the column effluent flows directly into the mass spectrometric vacuum system via a tube. Mainly, the most straightforward method of linking LC and MS appears to be the direct introduction.³³ In this section, we have discussed the LC-MS methods for the determination of RFX in a dosage form Table 19.

Table 19. Summary of LC-MS methods for the determination of RFX in a dosage form

Sr. No	Drug	Matrix	Stationary Phase	Mobile Phase	Internal Standard	Linearity (µg/mL)	Ref.
1	RFX	***	Shimpak ods C18 column	Acetonitrile/0.05% phosphoric acid (35:65)	***	2–36 µg/ml	144
2	RFX	Bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms	Symmetry C18 analytical Column	Acetonitrile–water (50:50, v/v)	Chlorophenyl methyl sulphone	125 to 500 µg/ml	145
3	TZN and RFX	Tablets	Spherisorb ODS column	Triethylamine : acetonitrile 55:45% (v/v)	Nimesulide	0.1–0.5 µg/ml 1.2–6.0 µg/ml	146

***** Not Provided**

HPLC method for RFX

The specificity of the HPLC method is excellent and simultaneously sufficient precision is also attainable. However, it has to be stated that the astonishing specificity, precision, and accuracy are attainable only if wide-ranging system suitability

tests are carried before the HPLC analysis. For this reason, the expense to be paid for the high specificity, precision, and accuracy is also high. The summary of the reported HPLC methods is shown in Table 20.

Table 20: Summary of HPLC methods for the determination of RFX in a single and combined dosage form

Sr. No	Drug name	Column	Mobile phase	Lambda max (nm)	Linearity (µg/mL)	Retention Time (min)	Flow rate (mL/min)	Detector	Ref.
1	RFX	C18 analytical column	Water: Acetonitrile (55:45 v/v)	366 nm	10-60 µg/ml	7.5 to 8 min	1 ml/min	UV-Vis spectrophotometer	147
2	RFX	Apollo C18 analytical column	Methanol and water (45:55 % v/v)	260 nm	24-120 mg/ml	2.379 ±0.02 min	0.8 ml/min	UV spectrophotometer	148
3	RFX	ODS C-18 column	Methanol : Water (50:50)	230 nm	2-40 µg/ml	7.79–8.00 min	1 ml/min	UV-Vis Detector	149
4	RFX and TNZ	Luna C-18 column	Methanol : Phosphate Buffer (55:45 v/v)	240 nm	7.5-17.5 µg/ml and 0.6-1.4 µg/ml	4.53 min and 5.92 min	1 ml/min	UV-Vis Detector	150
5	RFX and TNZ	Wakosil C-18 column	Acetonitrile : phosphate buffer (50:50 v/v)	240 nm	50-200 µg/ml and 10-80 µg/ml	4.9 min and 12.2 min	0.5 ml/min	UV-Vis Detector	151
6	PCT and RFX	Hypersil C-18 column	20mM phosphate buffer : Acetonitrile (55:45 v/v)	254 nm	7-13 µg/ml and 0.35-0.65 µg/ml	2.61 min and 10.49 min	1 ml/min	UV-Vis Detector	152
7	TNZ and RFX	Kromasil C-18 column	Phosphate buffer ph. 5.5 and methanol (45:55 v/v)	235 nm	10–200_g/ml and 100–2000_g/ml	3.199 min and 7.109 min	1 ml/min	UV detector	153

HPTLC method for RFX

Thin-layer chromatography is a popular technique for the analysis of a wide variety of organic and inorganic materials, because of its distinctive advantages such as minimal sample clean-up, a wide choice of mobile phases, flexibility in sample distinction, high sample loading capacity and low

cost. The summary of the reported HPTLC methods is shown in Table 21.

Table 21: Summary of HPTLC methods for the determination of RFX in a single and combined dosage form

Sr. No.	Drug	Stationary Phase	Mobile Phase	Detection	Linearity	Ref.
1	RFX and TZN	Precoated with silica gel 60F254 on aluminum sheets	Toluene: ethyl acetate: methanol: triethyl amine 6:3:0.5:0.1 (v/v/v/v)	235 nm	3.75 to 11.25 µg/spot 0.30 to 0.90 µg/spot	154
2	TZN and RFX	Merck HPTLC aluminum sheets of silica gel 60 F254	Toluene : methanol : acetone (7.5:2.5:1.0, v/v/v)	311 nm	10–100 ng/spot 100–1500 ng/spot	155
3	TZN and RFX	Precoated silica Gel G 60 F254 TLC plate	N- butyl acetate: formic acid: chloroform (6:4:2 v/v/v)	315 nm	2-10 mg/spot 16-80 mg/spot	156

LUMIRACOXIB:

Bio-analytical method for LMX

Bio-analysis is a sub-discipline of analytical chemistry covering the quantitative measurement of xenobiotics (drugs and their metabolites, and biological molecules in unnatural locations or

concentrations) and biotics (macromolecules, proteins, DNA, large molecule drugs, metabolites) in biological systems. The summary of the reported bioanalytical methods is shown in Table 22.

Table 22: Bioanalytical determination of LMX

Sr. No.	Drug	Sample Matrix	Method	Column	Detection	Internal Standard	Ref
1	LMX	Human Plasma	HPLC	Nucleosil C8 reversed-phase column	270 nm	Niflumic acid	157
2	LMX	Rat plasma	UHPLC–MS/MS	ACQUITY BEH C18 column	***	Diclofenac	158

*** Not Provided

UV-Visible spectroscopy method for LMX

The spectrophotometric methods have been accounted for the determination of LMX. The developed UV spectroscopy method is validated and therefore could be further used for quantitative analysis of lumiracoxib. Moreira, T.S., Pierre, M.B.R. , Fraga, C.A.M. , Sousa, VP established development and validation of HPLC and UV

spectrophotometric methods for the determination of lumiracoxib in tablets. The UV method was performed with ethanol as a solvent with the 2-30 µg/ml linearity. The UV method based on absorbance at 275 nm and the correlation coefficient (r²) is 0.999.(159)

Liquid-Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy methods (LC-MS) for LMX:

In recent years, the combination of LC/MS has gained a lot of attention for the analysis of interest analytes in complex samples with improved performance. In brief, after a thorough examination, LC/MS interfaces are divided into two categories namely interfaces for indirect and direct input of column effluent. A mechanical mechanism is employed to transmit the column effluent to the MS vacuum at an indirect introduction interface. A classic example of an

indirect introduction type of interface is the transportation system. In the case of the direct introduction system, the column effluent flows directly into the mass spectrometric vacuum system via a tube. Mainly, the most straightforward method of linking LC and MS appears to be the direct introduction. In this section, we have discussed the LC-MS methods for the determination of LMX in a dosage form Table 23.

Table 23. Summary of LC-MS methods for the determination of LMX in a dosage form

Sr. No	Drug	Matrix	Stationary Phase	Mobile Phase	Internal Standard	Linearity (µg/mL)	Ref.
1	LMX	Pharmaceutical formulations	Synergi Fusion C18 column	Phosphoric acid – acetonitrile (40:60 v/v)	Nimesulide	5–150 µg/ml	160
2	LMX	Pharmaceutical formulations	Synergi fusion C18 column	phosphoric acid : acetonitrile (40:60 v/v)	***	10–100 µg/mL	161

*** Not Provided

HPLC method for LMX

The specificity of the HPLC method is excellent and simultaneously sufficient precision is also attainable. However, it has to be stated that the astonishing specificity, precision, and accuracy are attainable only if wide-ranging system suitability tests are carried before the HPLC analysis. For this reason, the expense to be paid for the high specificity, precision, and accuracy is also high. The developed HPLC method is validated and therefore could be further used for quantitative analysis of lumiracoxib. Moreira, T.S., Pierre, M.B.R. , Fraga, C.A.M. , Sousa, VP established development and validation of HPLC and UV spectrophotometric methods for the determination of lumiracoxib in tablets. The HPLC method was performed on the chromatographic column was packed with propylsulfonic acid bonded with silica gel by using 10 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) - water – acetonitrile (10 : 40 : 50, v/v/v) as a mobile phase at flow rate 1.0 ml/min. The linearity of the drug is 2-30 µg/ml and the detection of drug at 278 nm by using UV detector.(159)

CONCLUSION

The present review article provides comprehensive data of various analytical and bioanalytical methods developed for Selective COX-2 Inhibitors alone and in combinations. For analysis purpose, different analytical methods have been reported that includes HPLC, HPTLC, UPLC, UV spectroscopy, etc. The method along with their details concerning the mobile phase, stationary phase, retention time, etc., have been summarized in tabular form that will more helpful for the researchers. In the future, enlisted data can be used for the development of analytical methods bio-analysis of Selective COX-2 inhibitors in pharmaceutical and biological formulations. Finally, it presents an opportunity for greater information on what has already been done and what new methods and changes can be developed to get a better estimation of Selective COX-2 inhibitors.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that no conflict of interest

ABBREVIATIONS

1. UV/VIS - Ultra violet/visible spectroscopy
2. HPLC - High-performance liquid chromatography
3. HPTLC - High-performance thin layer chromatography
4. LC-MS/MS - Liquid chromatography-mass spectroscopy-mass spectroscopy
5. UPLC - Ultra performance liquid chromatography
6. TLC - Thin layer chromatography
7. RP - Reverse phase
8. nm - Nanometer
9. µg/mL - Micro gram per Milliliter
10. PDA - Photo diode array
11. CXB - Celecoxib
12. ETX - Etoricoxib
13. VDX - Valdecoxib
14. PRX - Parecoxib
15. RFX - Rofecoxib
16. LMX - Lamiracoxib
17. REP - Repaglinide
18. DTX - Docetaxel
19. IBU - Ibuprofen
20. DIC - Diclofenac
21. NIF - Niflumic Acid
22. OH-CXB - Hydroxycelecoxib
23. COOH-CXB - Carboxycelecoxib
24. SCA - Salicylic acid
25. KPF - Ketoprofen
26. NMS - Nimesulide
27. DEZ - Dezocine
28. DEX - Dexmedetomidine
29. AMD - Amlodipine
30. CUR - Curcumin
31. ATV-Ca - Atorvastatin calcium
32. RMP - Ramipril
33. PCT - Paracetamol

34. RLZ - Riluzole
35. THC - Thiocholchicoside
36. PGBN - Pregabalin
37. TOP - Tolperisone
38. DRT - Drotraverine
39. TNZ - Tizanidine
40. OH-VDX - Hydroxylated valdecoxib
41. MSPC - Mosapride Citrate

REFERENCES:

1. Chow, H.H.S., Anavy, N., Salazar, D., Frank, D.H. and Alberts, D.S., 2004. Determination of celecoxib in human plasma using solid-phase extraction and high-performance liquid chromatography. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 34(1), pp.167-174.
2. Dongari, N., Sauter, E.R., Tande, B.M. and Kubátová, A., 2014. Determination of Celecoxib in human plasma using liquid chromatography with high resolution time of flight-mass spectrometry. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 955, pp.86-92.
3. Zhang, M., Moore, G.A., Gardiner, S.J. and Begg, E.J., 2006. Determination of celecoxib in human plasma and breast milk by high-performance liquid chromatographic assay. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 830(2), pp.245-248.
4. Zarghi, A., Shafaati, A., Foroutan, S.M. and Khoddam, A., 2006. Simple and rapid high-performance liquid chromatographic method for determination of celecoxib in plasma using UV detection: application in pharmacokinetic studies. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 835(1-2), pp.100-104.
5. Jalalizadeh, H., Amini, M., Ziaee, V., Safa, A., Farsam, H. and Shafiee, A., 2004. Determination of celecoxib in human plasma by high-performance liquid chromatography. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 35(3), pp.665-670.
6. Guirguis, M.S., Sattari, S. and Jamali, F., 2001. Pharmacokinetics of celecoxib in the

- presence and absence of interferon-induced acute inflammation in the rat: application of a novel HPLC assay. *Inflammation*, 1, p.4.
7. Reddy, M.N., Sujatha, P., Chauhan, A.S., Ramakrishna, S. and Diwan, P.V., 2003. A Simple And Sensitive Reverse-Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatographic Method For The Determination Of Celecoxib In Rat Plasma. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 65(3), p.260.
 8. Emami, J., FALAH, R. and Ajami, A., 2008. A rapid and sensitive HPLC method for the analysis of celecoxib in human plasma: application to pharmacokinetic studies.
 9. Rose, M.J., Woolf, E.J. and Matuszewski, B.K., 2000. Determination of celecoxib in human plasma by normal-phase high-performance liquid chromatography with column switching and ultraviolet absorbance detection. *Journal of Chromatography B: Biomedical Sciences and Applications*, 738(2), pp.377-385.
 10. Schönberger, F., Heinkele, G., Mürdter, T.E., Brenner, S., Klotz, U. and Hofmann, U., 2002. Simple and sensitive method for the determination of celecoxib in human serum by high-performance liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 768(2), pp.255-260.
 11. Jayasagar, G., Kumar, M.K., Chandrasekhar, K., Prasad, P.S. and Rao, Y.M., 2002. Validated HPLC method for the determination of celecoxib in human serum and its application in a clinical pharmacokinetic study. *Die Pharmazie*, 57(9), pp.619-621.
 12. Arabi, M., Ghaedi, M., Ostovan, A., Tashkhourian, J. and Asadallahzadeh, H., 2016. Synthesis and application of molecularly imprinted nanoparticles combined ultrasonic assisted for highly selective solid phase extraction trace amount of celecoxib from human plasma samples using design expert (DXB) software. *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry*, 33, pp.67-76.
 13. Praça, F.S.G., Bentley, M.V.L.B., Lara, M.G. and Pierre, M.B.R., 2011. Celecoxib determination in different layers of skin by a newly developed and validated HPLC-UV method. *Biomedical Chromatography*, 25(11), pp.1237-1244.
 14. Ansari, S., 2017. Application of hollow porous molecularly imprinted polymers using K₂Ti₄O₉ coupled with SPE-HPLC for the determination of celecoxib in human urine samples: optimization by central composite design (CCD). *Analytical Methods*, 9(21), pp.3200-3212.
 15. Werner, U., Werner, D., Pahl, A., Mundkowski, R., Gillich, M. and Brune, K., 2002. Investigation of the pharmacokinetics of celecoxib by liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry. *Biomedical Chromatography*, 16(1), pp.56-60.
 16. Han, D.G., Kwak, J., Seo, S.W., Kim, J.M., Yoo, J.W., Jung, Y., Lee, Y.H., Kim, M.S., Jung, Y.S., Yun, H. and Yoon, I.S., 2019. Pharmacokinetic evaluation of metabolic drug interactions between repaglinide and celecoxib by a bioanalytical HPLC method for their simultaneous determination with fluorescence detection. *Pharmaceutics*, 11(8), p.382.
 17. Hamama, A.K., Ray, J., Day, R.O. and Brien, J.A.E., 2005. Simultaneous determination of rofecoxib and celecoxib in human plasma by high-performance liquid chromatography. *Journal of chromatographic science*, 43(7), pp.351-354.
 18. Ziaei, E., Emami, J., Kazemi, M. and Rezazadeh, M., 2020. Simultaneous Determination of Docetaxel and Celecoxib in Porous Microparticles and Rat Plasma by Liquid-Liquid Extraction and HPLC with UV

- Detection: in vitro and in vivo Validation and Application. *Journal of Pharmacy & Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 23, pp.289-303.
19. Chamkouri, N., Zare-Shahabadi, V., Niazi, A. and Ramezani, M., 2004. Ibuprofen, diclofenac, and celecoxib quantification in human urine samples with ultrasound-assisted emulsification microextraction–HPLC and chemometrics.
 20. Navas, N., Urena, R. and Capitan-Vallvey, L.F., 2008. Determination of celecoxib, rofecoxib, sodium diclofenac and niflumic acid in human serum samples by HPLC with DAD detection. *Chromatographia*, 67(1), pp.55-61.
 21. Stormer, E., Bauer, S., Kirchheiner, J., Brockmoller, J. and Roots, I., 2003. Simultaneous determination of celecoxib, hydroxycelecoxib, and carboxycelecoxib in human plasma using gradient reversed-phase liquid chromatography with ultraviolet absorbance detection. *Journal of Chromatography B: Analytical Technologies in the Biomedical and Life Sciences*, 783(1), pp.207-212.
 22. Pavan Kumar, V.V., Vinu, M.C., Ramani, A.V., Mullangi, R. and Srinivas, N.R., 2006. Simultaneous quantitation of etoricoxib, salicylic acid, valdecoxib, ketoprofen, nimesulide and celecoxib in plasma by high-performance liquid chromatography with UV detection. *Biomedical Chromatography*, 20(1), pp.125-132.
 23. Abdel-Hamid, M., Novotny, L. and Hamza, H., 2001. Liquid chromatographic–mass spectrometric determination of celecoxib in plasma using single-ion monitoring and its use in clinical pharmacokinetics. *Journal of Chromatography B: Biomedical Sciences and Applications*, 753(2), pp.401-408.
 24. Ma, Y., Gao, S. and Hu, M., 2015. Quantitation of celecoxib and four of its metabolites in rat blood by UPLC-MS/MS clarifies their blood distribution patterns and provides more accurate pharmacokinetics profiles. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 1001, pp.202-211.
 25. Zheng, X., Wen, J., Liu, T.H., Ou-Yang, Q.G., Cai, J.P. and Zhou, H.Y., 2017. Genistein exposure interferes with pharmacokinetics of celecoxib in SD male rats by UPLC-MS/MS. *Biochemistry Research International*, 2017.
 26. Gika, H.G., Theodoridou, A., Michopoulos, F., Theodoridis, G., Diza, E., Settas, L., Nikolaidis, P., Smith, C. and Wilson, I.D., 2009. Determination of two COX-2 inhibitors in serum and synovial fluid of patients with inflammatory arthritis by ultra performance liquid chromatography–inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy and quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 49(3), pp.579-586.
 27. Hu, J., Su, X.J., Si, H.L., Song, R.X., Zhang, F., Qiu, X.J. and Chen, X.P., 2021. Simultaneous determination of celecoxib, dezocine and dexmedetomidine in beagle plasma using UPLC-MS/MS method and the application in pharmacokinetics. *Drug Design, Development and Therapy*, 15, p.2529.
 28. Damiani, P., Bearzotti, M. and Cabezón, M.A., 2003. A validated spectrofluorometric method for the determination of celecoxib in capsules. *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry*, 376(7), pp.1141-1146.
 29. Karajgi, S.R., Metri, S., Tiwari, V., Hulyalkar, S., Rub, T.A. and Patil, A.S., 2016. UV spectrophotometric method for the quantitative estimation of celecoxib in capsule dosage forms. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*, 8(10), pp.247-257.
 30. Saha, R.N., Sajeev, C., Jadhav, P.R., Patil, S.P. and Srinivasan, N., 2002. Determination

- of celecoxib in pharmaceutical formulations using UV spectrophotometry and liquid chromatography. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 28(3-4), pp.741-751.
31. Attimarad, M., Venugopala, K.N., Aldhubiab, B.E., Nair, A.B., SreeHarsha, N., Pottathil, S. and Akrawi, S.H., 2019. Development of UV spectrophotometric procedures for determination of amlodipine and celecoxib in formulation: use of scaling factor to improve the sensitivity. *Journal of Spectroscopy*, 2019.
32. Pathak, D.S., Pradhan, P.K., Meshram, D.B. and Patel, H.A., 2017. UV spectroscopic method for simultaneous estimation of celecoxib and amlodipine. *Pharmawave*, 10, pp.48-55.
33. Attala, K. and Elsonbaty, A., 2021. Smart UV spectrophotometric methods based on simple mathematical filtration for the simultaneous determination of celecoxib and ramipril in their pharmaceutical mixtures with amlodipine: A comparative statistical study. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 244, p.118853.
34. Attimarad, M., Narayanswamy, V.K., Aldhubaib, B.E., SreeHarsha, N. and Nair, A.B., 2019. Development of UV spectrophotometry methods for concurrent quantification of amlodipine and celecoxib by manipulation of ratio spectra in pure and pharmaceutical formulation. *PloS one*, 14(9), p.e0222526.
35. Mandale, T.R., Kondawar, M.S. and Kadam, S.D., 2020. Development and validation of analytical method for simultaneous estimation of amlodipine besylate and celecoxib in pure and combined dosage form. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech*, 13(9), pp.4280-4284.
36. Vijaya Bhaskar Reddy, A., Venugopal, N. and Madhavi, G., 2014. A selective and sensitive LC-MS/MS method for the simultaneous determination of twopotential genotoxic impurities in celecoxib. *Journal of Analytical Science and Technology*, 5(1), pp.1-8.
37. Rao, D.S., Srinivasu, M.K., Narayana, C.L. and Reddy, G.O., 2001. LC separation of ortho and meta isomers of celecoxib in bulk and formulations using a chiral column. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 25(1), pp.21-30.
38. Rao, R.N., Meena, S., Nagaraju, D., Rao, A.R. and Ravikanth, S., 2006. Liquid-chromatographic separation and determination of process-related impurities, including a regio-specific isomer of celecoxib on reversed-phase C18 column dynamically coated with hexamethyldisilazane. *Analytical sciences*, 22(9), pp.1257-1260.
39. Chandana, O.S.S. and Ravichandrababu, R., 2017. Stability indicating HPLC method for celecoxib related substances in solid dosage forms. *International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 7(1), pp.10-18.
40. Jadhav, A.S. and Shingare, M.S., 2005. A New Stability-Indicating RP-HPLC Method to Determine Assay and Known Impurity of Celecoxib API. *Drug development and industrial pharmacy*, 31(8), pp.779-783.
41. Dhabu, P.M. and Akamanchi, K.G., 2002. A stability-indicating HPLC method to determine celecoxib in capsule formulations. *Drug development and industrial pharmacy*, 28(7), pp.815-821.
42. Baboota, S., Faiyaz, S., Ahuja, A., Ali, J., Shafiq, S. and Ahmad, S., 2007. Development and validation of a stability-indicating HPLC method for analysis of celecoxib (CXB) in bulk drug and microemulsion formulations. *ACTA chromatographica*, 18, p.116.
43. Attimarad, M., Venugopala, K.N., SreeHarsha, N., Aldhubiab, B.E. and Nair, A.B., 2020. Validation of rapid RP-HPLC method for concurrent quantification of amlodipine and celecoxib in pure and

- formulation using an experimental design. *Microchemical journal*, 152, p.104365.
44. Gugulothu, D.B. and Patravale, V.B., 2012. A new stability-indicating HPLC method for simultaneous determination of curcumin and celecoxib at single wavelength: an application to nanoparticulate formulation. *Pharm Anal Acta*, 3(4), p.157.
45. Abdel Hamid, M.A., Mabrouk, M.M. and Michael, M.A., 2020. A fast and green reversed-phase HPLC method with fluorescence detection for simultaneous determination of amlodipine and celecoxib in their newly approved fixed-dose combination tablets. *Journal of Separation Science*, 43(16), pp.3197-3205.
46. Gadge, M.S. and Jagtap, V.G., Stability Indicating HPLC Method for Development and Validation of Simultaneous Estimation of Amlodipine and Celecoxib from Bulk and Marked Formulation.
47. Jadhav, P.S., Jamkar, P.M. and Avachat, A.M., 2015. Stability indicating method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of atorvastatin calcium and celecoxib in bulk and niosomal formulation by RP-HPLC. *Brazilian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 51, pp.653-661.
48. Shah, D.B., Patel, D.B.H. and Shah, D.J.S., Response Surface Methodology Based Development and Quantification of Celecoxib and Amlodipine Using RP-HPLC.(2022). *Int. J. Life Sci. Pharma Res*, 12(4), pp.P75-85.
49. Bapatu, H.R., Maram, R.K. and Murthy, R.S., 2015. Stability-indicating HPLC method for quantification of celecoxib and diacerein along with its impurities in capsule dosage form. *Journal of chromatographic science*, 53(1), pp.144-153.
50. Nagamani, P., Manjunath, S.Y. and Kumar, T.H., 2020. Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Estimation of Amlodipine Besylate and Celecoxib in Pharmaceutical Formulation. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 10(6), pp.31-36.
51. Sane, R., Pandit, S. and Khedkar, S., 2004. High-performance thin-layer chromatographic determination of celecoxib in its dosage form. *JPC-Journal of Planar Chromatography-Modern TLC*, 17(1), pp.61-64.
52. Attala, K., Eissa, M.S., El-Henawee, M.M. and Abd El-Hay, S.S., 2021. Application of quality by design approach for HPTLC simultaneous determination of amlodipine and celecoxib in presence of process-related impurity. *Microchemical Journal*, 162, p.105857.
53. Rajan, D.S., Bose, A., Gowda, K.V., Ghosh, A. and Pal, T.K., 2006. Development and validation of an HPLC method for analysis of etoricoxib in human plasma. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(4).
54. Ramakrishna, N.V.S., Vishwottam, K.N., Wishu, S. and Koteswara, M., 2005. Validated liquid chromatographic ultraviolet method for the quantitation of etoricoxib in human plasma using liquid-liquid extraction. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 816(1-2), pp.215-221.
55. Shakya, A.K. and Khalaf, N.A., 2007. High performance liquid chromatographic determination of Etoricoxib in human plasma. *Asian Journal of Chemistry*, 19(7), p.5241.
56. Radwan, M.A., Zaghoul, I.Y. and Abd Elbaky, N.A., 2009. Stability indicating high performance liquid chromatographic assay for the pharmacokinetics of cyclooxygenase (COX-2) inhibitor etoricoxib in rats. *African Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 3(7), pp.339-346.
57. Dalmora, S.L., Brum Junior, L., Ferretto, R.M., Oliveira, P.R.D., Barth, T. and Sangoi, M.D.S., 2008. Determination of etoricoxib in

- human plasma using automated on-line solid-phase extraction coupled with LC-APCI/MS/MS. *Química Nova*, 31, pp.574-578.
58. Bräutigam, L., Nefflen, J.U. and Geisslinger, G., 2003. Determination of etoricoxib in human plasma by liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry with electrospray ionisation. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 788(2), pp.309-315.
59. Jalakam, S.P., Waghmode, J., Pawar, P. and Mane, G., 2016. Development of Simple and Rapid LC-MS/MS Method for Determination of Etoricoxib in Human Plasma and its Application to Bioequivalence Study. *Biomirror*, 7.
60. Brum Junior, L., Cátia Ceni, D., Fronza, M., Renato de Oliveira, P. and Luiz Dalmora, S., 2006. Validation of an LC-tandem MS/MS method for the determination of etoricoxib in human plasma and pharmaceutical formulations. *Journal of liquid chromatography & related technologies*, 29(1), pp.123-135.
61. Werner, U., Werner, D., Hinz, B., Lambrecht, C. and Brune, K., 2005. A liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry method for the quantification of both etoricoxib and valdecoxib in human plasma. *Biomedical Chromatography*, 19(2), pp.113-118.
62. Pavan Kumar, V.V., Vinu, M.C., Ramani, A.V., Mullangi, R. and Srinivas, N.R., 2006. Simultaneous quantitation of etoricoxib, salicylic acid, valdecoxib, ketoprofen, nimesulide and celecoxib in plasma by high-performance liquid chromatography with UV detection. *Biomedical Chromatography*, 20(1), pp.125-132.
63. Zhang, X., Guo, N., Ji, W. and Wen, Q., 2019. Rapid quantitative analysis of etoricoxib in human plasma by UPLC-MS/MS and application to a pharmacokinetic study in Chinese healthy volunteers. *Biomedical chromatography*, 33(2), p.e4414.
64. Eure, W.D., Grossman, R.G., Horner, P.J. and Chow, D.S.L., 2021. LC-MS/MS assay of riluzole and etoricoxib in rat plasma and brain tissue with applications for sampling and evaluation in pre-clinical rat model of traumatic brain injury. *Talanta Open*, 4, p.100052.
65. Shahi, S.R., Agrawal, G.R., Rathi, P.B., Shinde, N.V., Somani, V.G., Mahamuni, S.B. and Padalkar, A.N., 2008. Development and validation of UV spectrophotometric method for the determination of etoricoxib in bulk and tablet formulation. *Rasayan J Chem*, 1(2), pp.390-394.
66. Chaple, D.R. and Bhusari, K.P., 2009. Spectrophotometric Methods for the Determination of Etoricoxib in Pharmaceutical Formulations. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, 2(3), pp.597-8.
67. Manideep, G., Shane, N.L.J., Pai, G. and Sathyanarayana, M.B., 2018. Development and validation of a UV spectroscopic method to estimate Etoricoxib in bulk and tablet formulation. *Research Journal of pharmacy and Technology*, 11(2), pp.758-760.
68. Singh, S., Mishra, A., Verma, A., Ghosh, A.K. and Mishra, A.K., 2012. A simple Ultraviolet spectrophotometric method for the determination of etoricoxib in dosage formulations. *Journal of advanced pharmaceutical technology & research*, 3(4), p.237.
69. Choudhari, V.P., Parekar, S.R., Chate, S.G., Bharande, P.D. and Kuchekar, B.S., 2011. Development and validation of UV-Visible spectrophotometric baseline manipulation methodology for simultaneous analysis of drotraverine and etoricoxib in pharmaceutical

- dosage forms. *Pharmaceutical methods*, 2(4), pp.247-252.
70. Acharjya, S.K., Rajesh, Y., Panda, P., Mallick, P. and Annapurna, M.M., 2010. Spectrophotometric methods for simultaneous estimation of etoricoxib and thiocolchicoside in bulk and combined pharmaceutical dosage form. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research*, 1(1), p.75.
71. Brum Jr, L., Fronza, M., Ceni, D.C., Barth, T. and Dalmora, S.L., 2006. Validation of liquid chromatography and liquid chromatography/tandem mass spectrometry methods for the determination of etoricoxib in pharmaceutical formulations. *Journal of AOAC International*, 89(5), pp.1268-1275.
72. Gangane, P.S., Bagde, S.M., Mujbaile, S.G., Niranjane, K.D. and Gangane, P., 2014. Development and Validation of HPLC assay method for etoricoxib in bulk drug and tablet formulation. *Indian J Nat Sci*, 4(24), pp.1565-1625.
73. Haque, M., Nasrin, S., Monir, M.M., Rahman, M.M. and Chowdhury, S., 2012. Method development and validation of RP-HPLC method of etoricoxib in bulk and its tablet dosage forms. *American Journal of PharmTech Research*, 2(6), pp.275-283.
74. Singh, B., Santhakumar, R., Bala, I., Prasad, S.B. and Verma, S., 2014. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for the dissolution and assay of etoricoxib in pharmaceutical dosage forms. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance*, 6(1), pp.1-7.
75. Bhattacharyya, I., Bhattacharyya, S.P., Sen, S. and Laha, T.K., 2009. Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatographic Method for the Analysis of Etoricoxib in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form. *Asian Journal of Research in Chemistry*, 2(3), pp.297-299.
76. Patel, H.M., Suhagia, B.N., Shah, S.A. and Rathod, I.S., 2007. Determination of etoricoxib in pharmaceutical formulations by HPLC method. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 69(5), p.703.
77. Rao, B.S. and Nagaraju, K.S., DEVELOPMENT, VALIDATION & STRESS DEGRADATION STUDIES OF ETORICOXIB USING DICLOFENAC AS AN INTERNAL STANDARD BY HPLC.
78. Shakya, A.K. and Khalaf, N.A., 2007. High Performance Liquid Chromatographic and Ultra Violet Spectroscopic Determination of Etoricoxib in Pharmaceutical Formulations. *Asian Journal of Chemistry*, 19(3), p.2059.
79. Bagade, S.B., Meshram, D.B. and Tajne, M.R., 2011. Estimation of Etoricoxib in tablet Dosage form by RP-HPLC using Internal Standard with Emphasize on Specificity parameter Method. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*, 27(2), p.697.
80. Topalli, S., Chandrashekhar, T.G. and Annapurna, M.M., 2012. Validated RP-HPLC method for the assay of etoricoxib (a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug) in pharmaceutical dosage forms. *E-Journal of chemistry*, 9(2), pp.832-838.
81. Venugopal, S., Tripathi, U.M. and Devanna, N., 2011. Validated Reverse Phase HPLC Method for the Determination of Impurities in Etoricoxib. *E-Journal of Chemistry*, 8(S1), pp.S119-S126.
82. Palte, D. and Kondalkar, A., 2015. Stability studies in combine dosage form of Etoricoxib and Thiocolchicoside using RP-HPLC. *Int J Res Stud Biosci*, 3(9), pp.163-70.
83. Singh, B., Chaudhary, A. and Sharma, A., 2022. RP HPLC Method Development for Simultaneous Estimation of Etoricoxib and Thiocolchicoside. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International*, pp.39-44.

84. Zaveri, M. and Khandhar, A., 2010. Quantitative determination of Etoricoxib and Paracetamol in pharmaceutical dosage form and in-vitro comparison by reversed-phase high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC). *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Health Care*, 2(4).
85. Kumar, S., Joshi, A., Thakur, R.S., Pathak, A.K. and Shah, K., 2011. Simultaneous estimation of etoricoxib and thiocolchicoside by RP-HPLC method in combined dosage forms. *Acta Poloniae Pharmaceutica*, 68(6), pp.839-843.
86. Narajji, C. and Karvekar, M.D., 2011. Method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of Paracetamol and Etoricoxib in pharmaceutical dosage form by RP-HPLC method. *Der Pharma Chem*, 3(4), pp.7-12.
87. Yeluri, R.R., Reddy, B.S. and Kumari, R.R., 2022. QUANTIFICATION OF PREGABALIN AND ETORICOXIB COMBO IN TABLETS AND BULK WITH DEVELOPED RP-HPLC METHOD: STABILITY INDICATING FEATURE ASSESSMENT. *Journal of Advanced Scientific Research*, 13(04), pp.31-36.
88. Padmavathi, K. and Rao, M.S., 2016. Development and validation of a new stability indicating liquid chromatographic method for the simultaneous determination of thiocholchicoside and etoricoxib in combined dosage form. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, pp.76-84.
89. Chaudhary, A. and Singh, B.K., 2021. Simultaneous Estimation of Pregabalin and Etoricoxib using Novel HPLC Method: An Application in Quantitative Analysis of Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms. *INDIAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH*, 55(3), pp.S837-S843.
90. Rao, K.P. and Ramana, G.V., 2014. Cost effective isocratic RP-HPLC method for simultaneous determination of Etoricoxib and Paracetamol in pure and in tablet formulation. *J Advan Stud Agric Biol Environ Sci*, 1(2), pp.201-209.
91. Andraws, G. and Trefi, S., 2020. Ionisable substances chromatography: A new approach for the determination of Ketoprofen, Etoricoxib, and Diclofenac sodium in pharmaceuticals using ion-pair HPLC. *Heliyon*, 6(8), p.e04613.
92. Pattan, S.R., Jamdar, S.G., Godge, R.K., Dighe, N.S., Daithankar, A.V., Nirmal, S.A. and Pai, M.G., 2009. RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of paracetamol and etoricoxib from bulk and tablets. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 1(1), pp.329-335.
93. Rani, K.S. and Parameshwar, P., 2021. METHOD DEVELOPMENT FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF ETORICOXIB AND THIOCOLCHICOSIDE IN TABLET FORMULATION BY RP-HPLC.
94. Goudar, N., Tejas, B., Badamane, M., Sathyanarayana, A.P. and Pai, V., 2022. QUANTITATIVE DETERMINATION AND VALIDATION OF ETORICOXIB AND PARACETAMOL COMBINED TABLET DOSAGE FORM BY REVERSE PHASE-HPLC. *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*, 15(3), pp.1702-1708.
95. Gupta, K.R., Likhari, A. and Wadodkar, S.G., 2010. Application of stability indicating HPLC Method for quantitative determination of etoricoxib and paracetamol in pharmaceutical dosage form. *Eurasian J. Anal. Chem*, 5(3), pp.218-226.
96. Solanki, R.V., Patel, R.B., Patel, R.K. and Sheth, R.A., 2022. Development and Validation of Fast and Robust Stability

- Indicating RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Tolperisone Hydrochloride and Etoricoxib in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*, 12(1), pp.56-61.
97. Sumithranandan, E.S.N. and Ajitha, M., 2022. A new validated method for the estimation of pregabalin and etoricoxib an using high performance liquid chromatography and of its degradation: <https://doi.org/10.54037/WJPS.2022.101001>. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, pp.1-11.
98. Shah, N.J., Shah, S.J., Patel, D.M. and Patel, N.M., 2006. Development and validation of HPTLC method for the estimation of etoricoxib. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(6), p.788.
99. Maheshwari, G., Subramanian, G.S., Karthik, A., Ranjithkumar, A., Ginjupalli, P.M.K. and Udupa, N., 2007. High-performance thin-layer chromatographic determination of etoricoxib in the bulk drug and in pharmaceutical dosage form. *JPC–Journal of Planar Chromatography–Modern TLC*, 20(5), pp.335-339.
100. Dhaneshwar, S.R., Raut, K.O. and Bhusari, V.K., 2011. Validated HPTLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Paracetamol and Etoricoxib in Bulk Drug and Formulation. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical & Biological Research (AJPBR)*, 1(2).
101. Rajmane, V.S., Gandhi, S.V., Patil, U.P. and Sengar, M.R., 2010. High-performance thin-layer chromatographic determination of etoricoxib and thicolchicoside in combined tablet dosage form. *Journal of AOAC International*, 93(3), pp.783-786.
102. Shetgar, S.S., Dharmasoth, R., Rao, B.M. and Keloth, B., 2022. RP-UPLC method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of Etoricoxib and Thiocolchicoside in tablets. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, 12(2), pp.144-151.
103. Sahu, P.K., Sankar, K.R. and Annapurna, M.M., 2011. Determination of Valdecocix in Human Plasma Using Reverse Phase HPLC. *E-Journal of Chemistry*, 8(2), pp.875-881.
104. Ramakrishna, N.V.S., Vishwottam, K.N., Wishu, S. and Koteswara, M., 2004. Quantitation of valdecocix in human plasma by high-performance liquid chromatography with ultraviolet absorbance detection using liquid–liquid extraction. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 802(2), pp.271-275.
105. Keshetty, S., Venisetty, R.K., Molmooori, V. and Ciddi, V., 2006. Determination of valdecocix in serum using a HPLC-diode array detector and its application in a pharmacokinetic study. *Die Pharmazie-An International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 61(3), pp.245-246.
106. Sane, R.T., Menon, S., Deshpande, A.Y. and Jain, A., 2005. HPLC determination and pharmacokinetic study of valdecocix in human plasma. *Chromatographia*, 61(3), pp.137-141.
107. Saccomanni, G., Giorgi, M., Del Carlo, S., Manera, C., Saba, A. and Macchia, M., 2011. Simultaneous detection and quantification of parecoxib and valdecocix in canine plasma by HPLC with spectrofluorimetric detection: development and validation of a new methodology. *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry*, 401(5), pp.1677-1684.
108. Chen, M., Sun, W., Wang, Z., Huang, C., Hu, G., Chen, Y. and Wang, L., 2020. Determination of parecoxib and valdecocix in rat plasma by UPLC-MS/MS and its application to pharmacokinetics studies. *BMC Pharmacology and Toxicology*, 21(1), pp.1-10.

109. Hu, J., Lv, B.F., Guo, W.J., Wang, B.W., Miao, D., Qiu, X.J. and Chen, X.P., 2020. Effects of dexmedetomidine on the pharmacokinetics of parecoxib and its metabolite valdecoxib in beagles by UPLC-MS/MS. *BioMed Research International*, 2020.
110. Liu, M., Yu, Q., Li, P., Zhu, M., Fang, M., Sun, B., Sun, M., Sun, Y., Zhang, P., He, Z. and Sun, J., 2016. Simultaneous determination of parecoxib sodium and its active metabolite valdecoxib in rat plasma by UPLC-MS/MS and its application to a pharmacokinetic study after intravenous and intramuscular administration. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 1022, pp.220-229.
111. Li, S.L., Zhu, Y.L., Zhu, C.Y., Li, S.B., Li, Z.H. and Qiu, X.J., 2020. Simultaneous determination of parecoxib and its metabolite valdecoxib concentrations in beagle plasma by UPLC-MS/MS and application for pharmacokinetics study. *Drug Design, Development and Therapy*, 14, p.1117.
112. Sutariya, V.B., Mashru, R., Sankalia, M.G. and Parikh, P., 2004. Spectrophotometric estimation of valdecoxib in pure form and tablets. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 66(3), p.360.
113. Suganthi, A., Sivakumar, H.B., Vijayakumar, S.C., Ravimathi, P. and Ravi, T.K., 2006. Visible spectrophotometric determination of valdecoxib in tablet dosage forms. *Indian Journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(3).
114. Nagulwar, V., Tajne, M.R., Upadhye, K., Bakhle, S. and Wadetwar, R., 2005. Simultaneous estimation of valdecoxib and tizanidine by Vierodt's and Q-analysis UV spectrophotometric method. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 67(5), p.624.
115. Raju, T.S., Raghavachary, K.S.V., Raghupathi Reddy, A., Satish Varma, M., Ravikumar, M. and Yadagiri Swamy, P., 2009. A validated and stability-indicating LC assay method for Valdecoxib. *Chromatographia*, 69(5), pp.507-511.
116. Sankar, A.S.K., An, K., Nagavalli, D., Palaniappan, M.S., Vetrichelvan, T. and Nithyan, K., 2007. Simultaneous spectrophotometric estimation of valdecoxib and tizanidine HCl in mixture. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 69(1), p.132.
117. Nagulwar, V., Dhurvey, Y.R., Upadhye, K., Bakhle, S. and Wadetwar, R., 2006. UV spectrophotometric simultaneous estimation of valdecoxib and paracetamol in combined tablet dosage form. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(5).
118. Fronza, M., Junior, L.B., Wrasse, M., Barth, T. and Dalmora, S.L., 2006. Development and Validation of a RP-HPLC Method for the Quantitation and Dissolution Studies of Valdecoxib. *Acta Farmaceutica Bonaerense*, 25(1), p.117.
119. Bhavsar, A.S., Talele, G.S., Fursule, R.A. and Surana, S.J., 2006. RP-HPLC estimation of paracetamol and valdecoxib in combined dosage form. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(5).
120. Ramaa, C.S., Shirode, A.R., Wamorkar, V.V., Kakad, A.B. and Kadam, V.J., 2006. Reverse-phase high performance liquid chromatographic determination of Tizanidine and Valdecoxib in tablets. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(4).
121. Karthikeyan, K., Saravanan, R., Rajeswari, R. and Pillai, K.C., 2009. Validation of single isocratic HPLC method for the assay of valdecoxib and determination of metaisomer impurity. *Journal of chromatographic science*, 47(4), pp.309-314.
122. Zečević, M., Savić, G. and Živanović, L., 2006. Development and validation of liquid chromatography method for the separation of

- valdecoxib and its sc-77852 impurity. *Analytical letters*, 39(9), pp.1875-1890.
123. Selvan, P.S., Gopinath, R., Saravanan, V.S. and Gopal, N., 2006. Simultaneous estimation of tizanidine and valdecoxib in combined dosage forms by RP-HPLC method. *Asian Journal of Chemistry*, 18(4), p.2505.
124. Subramanian, G., Faisal, M., Bhat, V., Kumar, A.R. and Udupa, N., 2006. Simultaneous RP-HPLC estimation of Tizanidine and Valdecoxib in tablets. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(3).
125. Bhavsar, A.S., Talele, G.S., Fursule, R.A. and Surana, S.J., 2006. RP-HPLC estimation of tizanidine HCl and valdecoxib in combined dosage forms. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(5).
126. Puranik, M., Wadher, S.J., Dhole, S. and Yeole, P.G., 2006. Simultaneous estimation of valdecoxib and tizanidine hydrochloride in tablets by RP-HPLC. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(5).
127. Ravi, T.K., Gandhimathi, M., Suganthi, A. and Sarovar, S., 2006. Forced-degradation study of valdecoxib as bulk drug and in tablet formulation by HPTLC. *Journal of separation science*, 29(11), pp.1647-1652.
128. Gandhimathi, M., Ravi, T.K., Shukla, N. and Sowmiya, G., 2007. High Performance Thin Layer Chromatographic Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Paracetamol and Valdecoxib in Tablet Dosage Form. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 69(1).
129. Sivasubramanian, L. and Devarajan, K.E.B., 2009. HPTLC for the simultaneous determination of Tizanidine and Valdecoxib in pharmaceutical dosage form. *Journal of Pharmacy Research*, 2(1).
130. Saccomanni, G., Giorgi, M., Del Carlo, S., Manera, C., Saba, A. and Macchia, M., 2011. Simultaneous detection and quantification of parecoxib and valdecoxib in canine plasma by HPLC with spectrofluorimetric detection: development and validation of a new methodology. *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry*, 401(5), pp.1677-1684.
131. Shaikh, S.M.T., Manjunatha, D.H., Seetharamappa, J. and Kandagal, P.B., 2007. High-Performance Liquid Chromatographic Determination of Parecoxib in Human Plasma and Pharmaceutical Formulations. *Analytical letters*, 40(15), pp.2925-2934.
132. Jin, X., Zhou, F., Liu, Y., Cheng, C., Yao, L., Jia, Y., Wang, G. and Zhang, J., 2018. Simultaneous determination of parecoxib and its main metabolites valdecoxib and hydroxylated valdecoxib in mouse plasma with a sensitive LC-MS/MS method to elucidate the decreased drug metabolism of tumor bearing mice. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 158, pp.1-7.
133. Li, S.L., Zhu, Y.L., Zhu, C.Y., Li, S.B., Li, Z.H. and Qiu, X.J., 2020. Simultaneous determination of parecoxib and its metabolite valdecoxib concentrations in beagle plasma by UPLC-MS/MS and application for pharmacokinetics study. *Drug Design, Development and Therapy*, 14, p.1117.
134. Liu, M., Yu, Q., Li, P., Zhu, M., Fang, M., Sun, B., Sun, M., Sun, Y., Zhang, P., He, Z. and Sun, J., 2016. Simultaneous determination of parecoxib sodium and its active metabolite valdecoxib in rat plasma by UPLC-MS/MS and its application to a pharmacokinetic study after intravenous and intramuscular administration. *Journal of Chromatography B*, 1022, pp.220-229.
135. Amini, M., Hamedani, M.P., Vosooghi, M., Nabavi, M. and Shafiee, A., 2005. Pre-column derivatization of rofecoxib for determination in serum by HPLC. *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry*, 382(5), pp.1265-1268.

136. DemİrtÜrk, E., Nemetlu, E., Şahİn, S. and Öner, L., 2020. Development and validation of an HPLC method for determination of rofecoxib in bovine serum albumin smicrospheres. *Turkish Journal of Chemistry*, 44(3), pp.647-655.
137. Sattari, S. and Jamali, F., 2000. High performance liquid chromatographic determination of cyclooxygenase II inhibitor rofecoxib in rat and human plasma. *J Pharm Pharmaceut Sci*, 3(3), pp.312-316.
138. Savaşer, A., Özkan, Y., Özkan, C.K., Taş, Ç. and Özkan, S.A., 2004. RP-HPLC Assay of Rofecoxib from Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms and Human Plasma and Its Drug Dissolution Studies. *Analytical letters*, 37(1), pp.81-97.
139. Woolf, E., Fu, I. and Matuszewski, B., 1999. Determination of rofecoxib, a cyclooxygenase-2 specific inhibitor, in human plasma using high-performance liquid chromatography with post-column photochemical derivatization and fluorescence detection. *Journal of Chromatography B: Biomedical Sciences and Applications*, 730(2), pp.221-227.
140. Hamama, A.K., Ray, J., Day, R.O. and Brien, J.A.E., 2005. Simultaneous determination of rofecoxib and celecoxib in human plasma by high-performance liquid chromatography. *Journal of chromatographic science*, 43(7), pp.351-354.
141. Navas, N., Urena, R. and Capitan-Vallvey, L.F., 2008. Determination of celecoxib, rofecoxib, sodium diclofenac and niflumic acid in human serum samples by HPLC with DAD detection. *Chromatographia*, 67(1), pp.55-61.
142. Werner, U., Werner, D., Mundkowski, R., Gillich, M. and Brune, K., 2001. Selective and rapid liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry method for the quantification of rofecoxib in pharmacokinetic studies with humans. *Journal of Chromatography B: Biomedical Sciences and Applications*, 760(1), pp.83-90.
143. Rajput, S.J., Sankalia, M.G. and Patel, F.T., 2005. Spectrofluorophotometric determination of rofecoxib and mosapride citrate in their individual dosage form. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 67(5), p.582.
144. Shehata, M.A., Ashour, A., Hassan, N.Y., Fayed, A.S. and El-Zeany, B.A., 2004. Liquid chromatography and chemometric methods for determination of rofecoxib in presence of its photodegradate and alkaline degradation products. *Analytica chimica acta*, 519(1), pp.23-30.
145. Radhakrishna, T., Rao, D.S. and Reddy, G.O., 2001. LC determination of rofecoxib in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 26(4), pp.617-628.
146. Gandhimathi, M., Ravi, T.K. and Varghese, S.J., 2005. Simultaneous LC determination of tizanidine and rofecoxib in tablets. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 37(1), pp.183-185.
147. Lalla, J.K., Hamrapurkar, P.D., Yadav, S.P. and Vyas, P.M., 2004. An improved HPLC method of analysis of rofecoxib. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 66(3), p.338.
148. Tadikonda, Y.K. and Dhanalakshmi, M., RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation of Rofecoxib in Bulk and Dosage Form.
149. Nagoji, K.V., Vijayasrinivas, S., Kumar, M.K., Mathivanan, N., Kumar, M.S. and Rao, M.B., 2004. A new reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method for analysis of rofecoxib in tablets. *Indian*

- journal of pharmaceutical sciences, 66(1), p.129.
150. Subramanian, G. and Udupa, N., 2004. RP-HPLC estimation of rofecoxib and tizanidine in combination tablets. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 66(5), p.699.
151. Pai, P.S. and Khan, H., 2005. HPLC method for Simultaneous estimation of Rofecoxib and Tizanidine hydrochloride in Tablets. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 67(4), p.504.
152. Subramanian, G., Sheety, R., Agarwal, S. and Udupa, N., 2005. Simultaneous reverse phase HPLC estimation of paracetamol and rofecoxib in tablets. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 67(2), p.247.
153. Kaul, N., Dhaneshwar, S.R., Agrawal, H., Kakad, A. and Patil, B., 2005. Application of HPLC and HPTLC for the simultaneous determination of tizanidine and rofecoxib in pharmaceutical dosage form. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 37(1), pp.27-38.
154. Pawar, U.D., Sulebhavikar, A.V., Naik, A.V., Pingale, S.G. and Manganonkar, K.V., 2009. Simultaneous determination of rofecoxib and tizanidine by HPTLC. *E-Journal of Chemistry*, 6(1), pp.295-302.
155. Kaul, N., Dhaneshwar, S.R., Agrawal, H., Kakad, A. and Patil, B., 2005. Application of HPLC and HPTLC for the simultaneous determination of tizanidine and rofecoxib in pharmaceutical dosage form. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 37(1), pp.27-38.
156. Ravi, T.K., Sireesha, K.R. and Jacob, S., 2006. HPTLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Tizanidine and Rofecoxib in tablets. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(2).
157. Cheremina, O., Brune, K. and Hinz, B., 2006. A validated high-performance liquid chromatographic assay for determination of lumiracoxib in human plasma. *Biomedical Chromatography*, 20(10), pp.1033-1037.
158. Sun, J., Zhang, L., Zhang, L. and Liu, Q., 2021. A validated UHPLC-MS/MS method for simultaneous determination of lumiracoxib and its hydroxylation and acyl glucuronidation metabolites in rat plasma: Application to a pharmacokinetic study. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 201, p.114105.
159. Moreira, T.S., Pierre, M.B.R., Fraga, C.A.M. and Sousa, V.P., 2008. Development and validation of HPLC and UV spectrophotometric methods for the determination of lumiracoxib in tablets. *Revista de Ciências Farmacêuticas Básica e Aplicada*, 29(3).
160. Sangoi, M.S., Wrasse-Sangoi, M., Oliveira, P.R. and Bernardi, L.S., 2011. Determination of lumiracoxib by a validated stability-indicating MEKC method and identification of its degradation products by LC-ESI-MS studies. *Journal of separation science*, 34(15), pp.1867-1874.
161. Oliveira, P.R., Bernardi, L.S., Mendes, C., Sangoi, M.S. and Silva, M.A., 2010. Liquid chromatographic determination of lumiracoxib in pharmaceutical formulations. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 51(3), pp.728-732.
162. <https://cdsco.gov.in/opencms/resources/UploadCDSCOWeb/2018/UploadConsumer/banneddrugs.pdf>

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